

An Automated Approach for Market Basket Analysis using Apriori Algorithm

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Abstract— Market basket analysis is a technique that aids businesses in understanding consumer purchasing patterns by seeing relationships between the items customers put in their shopping baskets. In many organizations, this analysis not only helps with decision-making but also boosts sales. This is done using the apriori algorithm. Market basket analysis aims to identify the products that customers regularly buy together, where "frequent items" refers to sets of products that match a user-specified criteria.

Keywords—Market Basket Analysis, Apriori Algorithm, Association Rule mining

I. INTRODUCTION

The exponential growth of digital data has resulted in the generation of terabytes of commercial data every second. It has become extremely difficult for the data management and mining communities to extract valuable information from this large amount of data as a result of the dramatic increase in data volume. Large amounts of consumer transaction data are gathered and stored by many organizations, yet having this data by itself does not always result in useful commercial insights. Market basket analysis was created as a result of the necessity for business industries to extract knowledge and relevant information from this data. By discovering relationships between the many goods that customers put in their shopping baskets, this study aids businesses in learning important details about their customers' purchasing habits. Finding out which items clients usually buy together is the primary goal of market basket analysis.

Association rules are a frequent name for market basket analysis, and one of the algorithms used in this technique is the Apriori algorithm. The aim of this study was to gain insight into the resulting concept, rule processing, and the rules obtained. The research provides a valuable learning experience for identifying patterns and associations in data.

II. APRIORI ALGORITHM

R. Agrawal and R. Srikant originally presented the algorithm in 1994 [4]. Apriori follows a level-wise search approach where it uses k-item sets to explore (k + 1)-item sets. The algorithm works by first identifying the 1-itemsets by searching the database for items that meet the minimal support requirement. Following that, the frequent 1-item sets are used to identify the frequent 2-item sets, and so on, until the frequent k-item sets are identified. The anti-monotonicity property of Apriori, which stipulates that any subset of a frequent item set must likewise be frequent, is one of its most

important characteristics. The program frequently counts the candidate items using a breadth-first search strategy.

The joining phase and the pruning step are the two key stages of the Apriori algorithm.

- In the joining step, a set of candidate k-item sets is generated by joining (L_k-1) with itself.
- In the pruning step, any (k-1)-item set that is not frequent cannot be a subset of the frequent k-item set. This helps to reduce the search space and speed up the algorithm.

Overall, the Apriori algorithm is an effective and widely-used method for finding frequent item sets in data mining.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

Apriori and FP-Growth, two popular algorithms for market basket analysis, are thoroughly examined by Maliha Hossain, A H M Sarowar Sattar, and Mahit Kumar [3]. The theoretical background of both algorithms and compare their performance based on execution time, memory usage, and number of frequent item sets generated. The study also includes an experimental evaluation of the algorithms using a real-world dataset, which shows that FP-Growth outperforms Apriori in terms of both efficiency and scalability. The paper ends with a discussion on the practical implications of the findings for businesses looking to leverage market basket analysis for decision making and business intelligence.

According to Warnia Nengsih [5], Data mining methods like Association Rules are used to find connections between objects. Rules are developed to ascertain the frequency of data occurrence in the item set, making it simpler to understand the significance of each data. An illustration of one of these algorithms is the Apriori algorithm. This paper compares market basket analysis with and without the Apriori algorithm in an effort to create rules for creating new information. The concept, the rule-making process, and the final rules are all taken into account in the comparison. Although the methods for developing rules differ, the results suggest that both approaches make use of the same concept. However, the ensuing laws are unchanged.

Market basket analysis, according to Tan P. N., Steinbach, M., and Kumar V [6], is a data mining technique used to find relationships between items. It can be used as a useful tool for decision-making by analyzing the potential percentage of the relation of the combined items in order to

learn new information. Numerous algorithms can be used for market basket analysis.

In market basket analysis, the rules of the relationship between items are typically expressed in the format of "A -> B", where A and B are disjoint item sets that is $A \cap B = \emptyset$.

Association analysis typically follows a basic methodology that includes the following steps:

a. Support

Determine the total percentage of the following two items: The combined percentage of two items is calculated to find the set of items that satisfy the minimal standard of support value. The following formula can be used to calculate an item's support value:

$$S(A) = \frac{\text{Number of transactions containing A}}{\text{Total number of transactions}}$$

The following will be the support value formula for two items:

$$S(A \cap B) = \frac{\text{Number of transactions of A\&B}}{\text{Total number of transactions}}$$

b. Confidence

It is computed as how frequently item Y appears in transactions that also contain item X.

$$\text{Confidence} = \frac{\text{Number of transactions having both A and B}}{\text{Number of transactions containing A}}$$

IV. METHODOLOGY

A. Data Preprocessing

To begin analyzing the Store dataset, we initially checked for any 'NaN' values, indicating that particular transaction did not involve the purchase of the item represented by the column. These were swapped with 0 to ensure consistency. Subsequently, quantity of non-replicating data, we then identified all unique items in the dataset. If the Store sells a wide variety of unique items, we utilized the Transaction Items per transaction are mapped using an encoder approach. Essentially, Transaction Encoder assigns a value of 1 to a product if it is present in a transaction, and 0 otherwise.

B. Methods for Mining Common Itemsets

The Apriori approach is used to find common item sets and the associated association rule in a dataset.

Fig. 1. System Architecture

The analysis is done on users who were logged into an e-commerce platform. The market basket analysis is a method for examining the relationships between items purchased by customers in a transaction. The main objective is to find out which items are usually bought together and to suggest additional items to the customers. The code starts by fetching the currently logged-in user and loading the orders whose products belong to the user. The order data will be in a transaction format. It creates a dictionary where the keys are users, and the values are the list of products bought by the users. The mlxtend library perform the market basket analysis on the transactional data. The Transaction Encoder class converts the transaction data into a binary matrix format. The binary matrix indicates whether a product was bought in a transaction or not. The apriori function is then used to generate frequent item sets from the binary matrix data. The minimum support parameter is set to 0.01, which means that only item sets with a minimum support of 1% will be considered frequent. The frequent item sets generated are then used to generate association rules using the association rules function from the mlxtend library. The metric parameter is set to "lift," which measures the strength of the association between items. Only rules with a lift value greater than 1 will be taken into consideration because the minimum threshold parameter is set to 1.

V. RESULT

The result displays the market basket analysis using the apriori method with a minimum support of 0.01 to locate

common item sets and extracts association rules with a minimum lift threshold of 1.

Antecedents	Consequents	Support	confidence	Lift
frozenset({'Cotton Knit Half Sleeves T-Shirt Surfs On Print - Orange'})	frozenset({'Cotton Yarn Dyed Singlet Checks Frock - Lennon Green'})	0.5	0.5	1.0
frozenset({'Cotton Yarn Dyed Singlet Checks Frock - Lennon Green'})	frozenset({'Cotton Knit Half Sleeves T-Shirt Surfs On Print - Orange'})	0.5	1.0	1.0
frozenset({'Cotton Knit Half Sleeves T-Shirt Surfs On Print - Orange'})	frozenset({'Jamican Shorts - Grey'})	1.0	1.0	1.0
frozenset({'Jamican Shorts - Grey'})	frozenset({'Cotton Knit Half Sleeves T-Shirt Surfs On Print - Orange'})	1.0	1.0	1.0

VI. CONCLUSION

The technique discussed in the paper identifies links between the things customers put in their shopping baskets, which aids organizations in understanding consumer purchase behavior. To find out which things people usually buy together, Apriori technique can be used to find frequent item sets.. Many organizations can use the knowledge gained from this analysis to make wise decisions and boost sales. Market Basket Analysis has developed into a crucial tool for companies in a range of industries by utilizing the strength of association rules.

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